

An *in situ* investigation of microscopic infusion and void transport during vacuum-assisted infiltration by means of X-ray computed tomography

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Abstract

In situ vacuum-assisted infiltration experiments were carried out using synchrotron X-ray computed tomography (SXCT) to study the mechanisms of microfluid flow within a fiber tow. A single tow of E glass fibers was infused with a water and syrup blend using an apparatus designed and built for this purpose. The high resolution of the SXCT images allows the detailed reconstruction of individual fibers within the tow while the contrast between the different phases (air, fluid and fibers) was enough to track the fluid front position and shape as well as the void transport during infiltration. The ability of this technique to provide detailed information of microfluid flow and void transport in composite materials is clearly established. The fluid propagation at the microscopic level as well as the mechanisms of void transport within the tow were related to the wetting between the fluid and the fibers, the rheological properties of the fluid and the local microstructural details (fiber

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volume fraction, fiber orientation) of the fiber tow.

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1. Introduction

Liquid moulding technologies, such as resin transfer molding (RTM) and vacuum resin infusion (VARI), are widely used for manufacturing of complex composite parts in different industrial sectors. In this strategy, resin is infiltrated into the dry fiber preform by means of a pressure gradient between the inlet and outlet gates. A major limitation of liquid moulding is the generation of voids and air entrapments during infiltration, which reduce significantly the mechanical properties of the composite. Macrodefects, resulting from dry –or poorly impregnated– zones, appear when the resin flow reaches the outlet gate before completely filling the component. They are due to an inadequate distribution of the injection/infusion/venting ports in the component. In addition, microdefects (voids) can also appear, even if the part has been completely filled with resin during infusion. Standard reinforcements used in composite manufacturing are formed by tows containing thousands of fibers in specific fabric architectures (unidirectional, woven, non-crimp, stitched, etc.), leading to microporosity (the free space in between individual fibers within the tow) and macroporosity (the free space between tows). Viscous flow dominated by the resin pressure gradient takes place through the high permeable channels between adjacent fiber tows while tow impregnation perpendicular to the fiber is mainly driven by capillary forces if the fibers are wetted by the liquid. This dual-scale flow (micro-meso) is partially responsible for the generation of voids during liquid moulding of composite parts because of the competition between viscous and capillary forces (Lawrence et al., 2009; Kuentzer et al., 2007; Patel and Lee, 1996a,b).

Previous experimental observations have demonstrated that void formation in engineering composites depends on the ratio between viscous and capillary forces through the non-dimensional modified capillary number, Ca^* (Patel and Lee, 1995; Park et al., 2011; Ravey et al., 2014; Hamidi et al., 2004)

$$Ca^* = \frac{\mu \bar{v}}{\gamma \cos \theta} \quad (1)$$

where μ and \bar{v} stand, respectively, for the resin viscosity and the average resin velocity, while γ and θ are the fluid surface tension and the contact angle, respectively. An optimum capillary number to minimize the void content has been found in specific material systems (Hamidi et al., 2004). Viscous forces are dominant with respect to capillary ones for large capillary numbers ($Ca^* > 10^{-2}$) and the rapid flow of the resin through the tow-to-tow free gaps leads to the formation of voids within the tows, as air entrapments cannot escape. On the contrary, the fluid velocity between tows is smaller for low capillary numbers ($Ca^* < 10^{-3}$), and the wicking effects caused by the intra-tow capillary forces become dominant. Under these conditions, fiber tows are rapidly filled with resin and air entrapments are generated between tows.

Obviously, understanding the resin flow mechanisms is crucial to manufacture composite parts with minimum porosity by liquid moulding and the selection of the appropriate experimental technique to monitor accurately void generation and transport is a critical part of this process. Macroscopic resin flow measurements can be performed by direct image monitoring in transparent acrylic moulds during RTM (Patel and Lee, 1995; Kuentzer et al., 2006; Nowak and Chun, 1993) or on the surface of the vacuum bag in VARI (Lawrence et al., 2009). Vilà et al. (2014) tracked the position of the resin flow front in a VARI process by measuring the changes in the fabric thickness, associated with the resin-fabric stress transfer during infusion, by means of digital image correlation. Dielectric sensors (Neacsu et al., 2006) or embedded optical Bragg sensors, based on the change of the refractive index of the surrounding media when the fabric is infiltrated, can also be used to track resin flow and curing at discrete points (Gupta and Sundaram, 2009; Lekakou et al., 2006). Other authors have used C-scan ultrasounds when resin progress through the fabric (Thomas et al., 2008). The infusion experiments were carried out with the vacuum bag immersed in a water tank and the resin flow was stopped at different times. Fully and partially saturated regions were tracked by C-scan by averaging the signal attenuation in the through-the-thickness direction of the laminate. This technique can also be used to monitor the flow propagation in the through-the-thickness direction in thick fabrics to determine the out-of-plane permeability (Stoven et al., 2003). All these techniques provide valuable information about the macroscopic flow propagation in a composite part during the infusion/injection process but their low spatial resolution cannot analyze the microflow process within the tow.

To overcome these limitations, Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI) can be used to track the front flow by mapping the fluid concentration inside porous samples of cm dimensions (Leisen and Beckham, 2001). Neacsu et al. (2007) carried out MRI measurements to study capillary-driven transversal flow in bundles of aligned fibers using blends of water and corn syrup with protonated liquids. The evolution of the wet portion of the fiber bundle with respect to time was obtained and compared with analytical models of fluid propagation. Endruweit et al. (2011a,b) determined the local fluid concentration using MRI during impregnation of several fabrics, including woven, non-crimp and triaxial braids, detecting local variations attributed to the microvoid formation at the tow level as well as dry spots.

X-ray radiography has also been used to track the progress of the fluid during infiltration due to the difference of X-ray absorption coefficients between the fibers and the fluid (Bréard et al., 1999). The two-dimensional information provided by radiography can be very useful to track the progress of the fluid front but it is not suitable to analyze the development of porosity, particularly at the microlevel. X-ray computed tomography (XCT), in which a set of radiographies obtained during sequential sample rotation are used to obtain a three dimensional reconstruction of the object, is much more appropriate to track of porosity during infiltration. This technique has been successfully applied to study damage in composites (Sket et al., 2014; Seltzer et al., 2013), as well as to analyze the effect of processing conditions in the porosity of composite materials (Centea and Hubert, 2011, 2012; Hernández et al., 2011, 2013). Moreover, the resolution of this technique (in the range of μm) is adequate to detect intratow and intertow voids, including information about their size, shape and spatial distribution.

To the authors' knowledge, XCT has not been used to monitor the infiltration process at the microscale in composite materials and this work is intended to establish the advantages and limitations of this technique for this particular problem. To this end, a miniaturized apparatus for vacuum infusion was designed and built to study *in situ* the infiltration mechanisms operating at the micro-scale in a XCT synchrotron beamline. These conditions are representative of the fluid flow in textile preforms under low capillary numbers in which the wicking effects due to capillary forces are dominant with respect to viscous flow. The fluid propagation at the microscopic level as well as the mechanisms of void transport within the tow were related to the wetting between the fluid and the fibers, the rheological properties of the

fluid and the local microstructural features (local fiber volume fraction, fiber orientation) of the fiber tow.

2. Experimental techniques

The vacuum infusion apparatus was designed in such a way that the fluid is infiltrated from the top of a vertical single fiber tow while the outlet is placed at the bottom, Figure 1a). Thus, the device can be installed in the rotation stage of a XCT system. The miniaturized device allows to study small specimens consisting of one to three fiber tows within the detector field of view of the X-ray system (approximately 40 mm in length by 3.8 mm wide). An important feature of the device is the miniaturization of all the parts of the infusion process, including the inlet and outlet ports. The inlet was manufactured using a syringe needle of 0.8 mm in diameter which provides a reservoir of 20 ml and a piston system to control accurately the volume of infused fluid. The outlet was made using an open syringe of 0.8 mm in diameter previously cut and adjusted to the support, which is connected to the vacuum system.

The sample was a single fiber tow of 2K (1000 tex) extracted from a plain woven fabric of E glass (average fiber diameter $16 \pm 2 \mu\text{m}$), which was placed in between two standard vacuum bag films of about $64 \mu\text{m}$ in thickness (NBF-540-LFT) thermally sealed at the edges, Figure 1b). The vacuum bag and fiber tow assembly was 25 mm in length with an irregular cross-section of ≈ 4 mm in width and 0.5 mm in thickness, Figure 1c). The sample was placed between the inlet and the outlet, connecting both ends with the respective syringe needles, and sealed with standard tacky tape (LTT-90B). Thus, the sample contained in the vacuum bag film was completely sealed at the edges (by thermal sealing) and borders (by tacky tape) at the infusion and vacuum points. The whole system was mounted on an aluminum support connected to the vacuum system. Vacuum pressure of $\approx 0.91 \times 10^5$ Pa was applied with a rotatory vane pump connected to the vacuum line to avoid leaks during the tomographic measurements. The vacuum pressure was continuously monitored during the in situ experiment. The infusion tow was encapsulated within a PMMA cylinder (at atmospheric pressure inside the cylinder) to provide mechanical stability to the infusion device and to protect the X-ray system against fluid spills without significant X-ray attenuation.

The fluid infusion is controlled by a simple regulation system made up

of a screw and a nut with washer. Initially, the nut and the washer block the syringe piston preventing fluid propagation driven by the vacuum. The infusion driven by vacuum can progress by rotating the nut of the screw. In this way the flow front can be controlled accurately by adjusting the nut rotations and the total amount of fluid infused can be controlled step-by-step with the thread pitch. This is critical because any parasitic fluid propagation through the sample during the acquisition time of the tomograms (due to negligible leaks at the vacuum and infusion ports or other sources) will lead to image artifacts and blurring in the reconstructed volumes, that can preclude the adequate spatial resolution of the different phases (fibers, fluid and air entrapments). Gravitational effects could also be discarded (negligible Bond number Bo (LeBel et al., 2012)) for the size of the capillaries between individual fibers. The acquisition time for each tomogram was about 2 hours (see below).

A blend of water (30%) and syrup (70%) was used as infusion fluid. The blend was degassed immediately before the infiltration for 20 minutes in a vacuum container. The viscosity of the fluid, $\mu = 0.35 \text{ Pa}\cdot\text{s}$, was measured with a rotational viscosimeter Fungilab with L2 type spindle at 30 rpm at ambient temperature. The static fiber-fluid contact angle, $\theta = 78.5 \pm 6.5^\circ$, was measured optically with an OCA 15EC Neurtek apparatus while the surface tension, $\gamma \approx 80 \text{ mJ/m}^2$ was obtained from well-established values in the literature (Rust and Manga, 2002). Under these conditions, the modified capillary number during infusion can be estimated from eq. (1) as

$$Ca^* \approx \frac{K_{\parallel} \Delta p / \Delta x}{\gamma \cos \theta} \quad (2)$$

where $\Delta p \approx 0.7 \text{ atm}$ is the pressure gradient, $\Delta x \approx 2.5 \text{ cm}$ the average infusion length and $K_{\parallel} = 2.6 \times 10^{-12} \text{ m}^2$ the tow permeability parallel to the fibers that was obtained from the Gebart model for an average fiber volume fraction of 54% (Gebart, 1992). The average fiber volume fraction was calculated from the tomograms of the cross-sections along the tow. The fiber area was determined from the number of pixels corresponding to the fibers, which was divided by the total tow area. The average fiber volume fraction was fairly constant along the tow. According to eq. (2), $Ca^* \approx 6 \times 10^{-4}$, leading to a regime in which capillary forces are dominant over viscous forces.

The SXCT observation was focused in the infiltration mechanics during

the infusion process. The *in situ* experiment was performed at the P05 beam-line of PETRA III storage ring at the Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron (DESY) in Hamburg (Germany). The intense and coherent synchrotron beam was generated by an undulator which provides X-rays in energy range of 5 keV to 50 keV. A Si 111 double crystal monochromator was used to set the energy at 25 keV during the experiments. The flow was stopped by the blocked piston of the syringe and the infiltration device was rotated by 180° while recording the transmitted intensity by an X-ray CCD detector with an effective pixel size of 1.25 μm^2 . The volumes were reconstructed with binning 2 leading to an effective pixel size of 2.5 μm^2 . Motorized slits defined the horizontal and vertical beam sizes of 3.8 mm and 1.9 mm, respectively. Radiographies at different angles of the central region of the tow, located within the field of view of the X-ray system, were obtained three times during the experiment. The first one prior to infusion, the second one once the fluid front has advanced up to approximately the middle of the tow, and the third one after the tow was fully impregnated. Nine hundred radiographs with an exposure time of 300 ms each were collected in about 120 min. The sample to detector distance was set to 37 mm which provided some degree of phase contrast to the reconstructions. The three dimensional microstructure was reconstructed using the standard filtered back-projection algorithm.

3. Results and discussion

Infusion experiments were performed using the experimental set-up described above. The mesoscopic front flow had a triangular shape mainly due to the anisotropic permeability of the fiber bundle and to the point infusion, Figure 1b). According to the Gebart model (Gebart, 1992), the longitudinal permeability is at least one order of magnitude larger than the radial one for a fiber volume fraction of 54%, leading to a two dimensional flow. However, preferential propagation of the fluid along the tow/bag interface was observed in several tests, as in racetracking.

3.1. Local fluid flow mechanisms

Figure 2a) shows a cross section perpendicular to the fiber tow of the partially impregnated reconstructed volume where the different phases (fibers, fluid and voids) are clearly distinguished. It is worth noting that the high

resolution of the SXCT images allows the detailed reconstruction of individual fibers within the tow while impregnated and dry regions of the tow can be distinguished. A nearly constant fiber volume fraction of $\approx 54\%$ was measured from different cross sections along the tow. This volume fraction is representative of the typical conditions during vacuum infusion manufacturing. The fiber volume fraction was only locally disturbed when voids were dragged along the fiber direction, as shown below.

The reconstructed volume of ≈ 0.75 mm in length included 753 slices perpendicular to the tow and allowed a detailed 3D reconstruction of the flow front at the microscale. Representative tomograms of the central region of the tow prior, during and after filling are depicted in Figs. 2b, c and d), respectively. The fluid is represented in navy blue while the internal void within the tow is shown in red in Figure 2c). Air not corresponding to voids is shown as dark gray and fibers as light gray. The local distribution of fibers within the tow is inhomogeneous (fiber clusters and empty spaces are clearly shown) and fibers are not parallel and present convergent/divergent trajectories with significant twisting and meandering. As a result, flow progress along the bundle is inhomogeneous, leading to the formation of preferential channels in the fiber direction, Fig. 2c). Full impregnation of the tow is attained afterwards by the fluid flow perpendicular to the fibers from these preferential channels. This sequence in the infiltration mechanisms is triggered by the differences in permeability and capillary forces between both orientations, although the relative trajectories of neighbor fibers play an important role because fluid flow along the channel formed by two convergent fibers is arrested by the drag capillary forces, Figure 2e).

A first interesting observation provided by the *in situ* infusion experiments is related with the capillary forces and the shape of the meniscus formed at the flow front between adjacent fibers, Figure 3a). The local contact angle was measured at different positions across the fluid front, leading to an obtuse angle with an average value of $\approx 150^\circ$, which indicates a non-wetting condition between the fluid and the fibers. This value is different from static contact angle of 78.5° measured optically, as indicated above. Similar discrepancies during vacuum infusion have been reported by other authors. For instance, Li et al. (2010) studied the behavior of capillary forces during longitudinal impregnation of fiber tows subjected to external and vacuum-driven pressure gradients with several infiltration fluids. They found that the capillary pressure acted as a drag force for the infiltration

under vacuum-assisted conditions for several fluids but this effect was not found if the stress gradient for infiltration was produced with compressed air. These authors attributed this behavior to dynamic effects because the capillary number Ca^* during infiltration was large. Verrey et al. (2006) found similar dynamic effects on the contact angle, which were attributed to the fiber surface roughness increasing the real contact area or to the pinning of triple lines (gas-liquid-solid) by the sharp edges. Other authors (Karbhari and Palmese, 1997) attributed this effect to the interaction of fiber sizing with the wetting fluid.

It should be remarked that SXCT measurements were carried out under quasi-static conditions and no fluid displacements were detected during data acquisition because they would have led to image blurring effects. As a result, the discrepancies in the contact angle between vacuum infiltration and air measurements cannot be attributed to dynamic effects and they are more likely associated with surface effects induced by fiber sizing in vacuum. This non-wetting fluid-fiber interaction during vacuum infusion leads to important effects in the local microflow distribution. Transversal fluid flow is easier in those areas where the dragging force against the infiltration is lower, and thus coincides with the channels with faster longitudinal flow.

A detailed quantification of the variations of the capillary pressure and the permeability was carried out from the local fiber volume fraction, V_f , obtained from SXCT. The fiber centers as well as their radius were determined and the local fiber volume fraction in the transversal section of the tow was computed assuming a fixed spot size equal to a fiber diameter. This spot size yields $V_f = \pi/4 = 78.5\%$ for a square-packed fiber arrangement. The local fiber volume fractions in three transverse cross-sections along the tow direction are shown in Figure 4b). It should be noted that the minima of the local volume fraction are found in the perimeter, while the maxima are located in the center.

From these estimations of the local fiber volume fraction, the non-dimensional capillary pressure, \bar{p}_c , was determined according to Ahn et al. (1991) and Pillai and Advani (1996) as

$$\bar{p}_c = \frac{p_c}{p_0} = \frac{V_f}{1 - V_f} \quad (3)$$

where $p_0 = F\gamma \cos \theta / D_f$ and F and D_f stand, respectively, for the shape

factor ($F = 4$ and $F = 2$ for longitudinal and transversal flow, respectively) and the fiber diameter, while γ and θ are the surface energy and contact angle. The term $\bar{p}_c = V_f/(1 - V_f)$ in equation (3) represents, therefore, the effect of the microstructure on the capillary pressure distribution within the tow. In addition, the longitudinal permeability K_{\parallel} of a set of unidirectional and parallel fibers was analytically derived by Gebart (1992) as a function of the fiber volume fraction as

$$\frac{K_{\parallel}}{D_f^2} = \frac{2}{57} \frac{(1 - V_f)^3}{V_f^2} \quad (4)$$

The longitudinal permeability factor, K_{\parallel}/D_f^2 and the non-dimensional capillary pressure, \bar{p}_c , are plotted in Fig. 4c) and d), respectively, for three cross-sections perpendicular to the tow at the same infusion time. The dry and wet regions in these cross sections at this instant are also shown in Fig. 4a). The regions in which the fiber volume fraction was low (mainly the tow perimeter) were areas of preferential longitudinal flow, leading to a kind of race tracking effect.

The differences in the capillary pressure between the regions with the highest ($\approx 80\%$) and lowest ($\approx 35\%$) fiber volume fraction were very large. Fluid flow in the transverse direction was not favored in regions with high fiber volume fraction while the longitudinal impregnation of the fiber clusters was impeded by the drag associated with the obtuse contact angle. Obviously, the mechanisms of microfluid flow in the transverse direction depended on the precise fiber distribution in both longitudinal and transversal orientations. As indicated above, fibers were not perfectly aligned in the tow direction and significant convergent/divergent trajectories were found. These irregularities facilitated the fluid propagation in the transversal direction even in areas containing a high volume fraction of packed fibers.

3.2. Void Transport

During tow impregnation, microvoids and macrovoids were found and their movement was followed from SXCT. data. Microvoids were generated by small inhomogeneities in the flow velocity in the tow cross section resulting in zones/channels where the fluid propagates faster. These differences in the velocity of the flow at the tow level were also shown in Figure 3. Elongated voids are formed as a result of the differences in the longitudinal flow within

the tows. The migration of the void along the tow is sometimes constrained by presence of two fibers with convergent trajectories that can trap the void and arrest the propagation, Fig. 3. These voids can escape from this trap in the longitudinal direction if the pressure gradient is large enough to push them along the constrained capillary channel. Otherwise, they will try to move along the transverse direction and the final transportation path depends on the different constraints, longitudinal and transverse, experience by the void towards the outlet gate.

Lundstrom (1996) determined analytically the pressure gradient $\Delta p = (p_1 - p_2)$ required to move a void of radius R_v through a constricted capillary tube of radius R_{con} , Figure 5, as

$$\Delta p = \frac{2\gamma \cos \theta}{R_{con}} \left(1 - \frac{R_{con}}{R_v} \right) \quad (5)$$

Assuming that the ratio R_v/R_{con} remains constant, eq. 5 indicates that the lower the capillary radius the larger the pressure gradient required to pull the void through the constriction. Thus, microvoids are much more prone to be trapped by the microstructure of the fiber bundle in the longitudinal direction and can only be evacuated by migration in the tow plane in which they will maintain some transversal mobility. As a consequence, small voids are rather difficult to evacuate in liquid moulding for the usual pressure gradients applied but the influence of small voids in the mechanical behavior of composite materials is much smaller than that of large voids, which can usually span dozens of fibers with a characteristic dimension in the range of the fiber tow thickness.

Bubbles resulting from minor air leaks at the inlet led to the formation of macrovoids, which were transported to the outlet gate during the *in situ* experiments. Initially, they were easily transported by the fluid flow, as compared with small voids, because the pressure differential to overcome the obstacles was much smaller. However, the bubble may be anchored along the trajectory because of various mechanisms (closed-packed fiber regions, fiber convergent trajectories, etc.), and the internal pressure has to rise to resume the propagation. As a result, the presence of the void led to an important perturbation of the fiber distribution as well as the vacuum bag. This is shown in Figure 6, which shows the cross sections of the fiber tow prior, during, and after the transport of a large void is depicted. It is important

to note that individual fibers did not return to the original position once the void passed through a given cross section and this effect can be probably attributed to the higher mobility of the fibers as a result of fluid lubrication. Very interestingly, the large void passed through the tow section, closing again the bag and leaving a trace of small voids that remained arrested after the process, delineating the original void contour, Figure 6c).

4. Conclusions

In situ VARI experiments were carried out in the synchrotron beam to study the mechanisms of microfluid flow within a fiber tow by means of SXCT. A single tow of E glass fibers was infused with a water and syrup blend using an apparatus designed and built for this purpose. The tow was impregnated in several steps by controlling the fluid volume delivered at the inlet needle and radiographies at different angles were taken after each step to reconstruct the three dimensional microstructure of the infiltrated tow. The high resolution of the SXCT images allows the detailed reconstruction of individual fibers within the tow while the contrast between the different phases (air, fluid and fibers) was enough to track the fluid front position and shape as well as the void transport during infiltration. The ability of this technique to analyze the details of microfluid flow and void transport in composite materials is clearly established.

The high resolution SXCT images showed an obtuse contact angles between the fluid and the fibers at the flow front. This behavior, which was opposed to the wetting contact angles measured in air, was also reported by other authors (Li et al., 2010; Verrey et al., 2006) and it cannot attributed to dynamic effects because the tomograms were acquired when the flow front was stopped. More likely, it seems to be a surface effect triggered in vacuum by the interaction between the fluid and the fiber sizing. One consequence of the phenomenon is that the capillary pressure acted as a drag force on the fluid flow. As a result, fluid flow was favored through areas with low fiber volume fraction which presented higher permeability and lower capillary forces. The complexity of the microflow depended markedly on the microstructure and the presence of convergent/divergent individual fiber trajectories played a significant role. Convergent fiber trajectories tend to arrest the fluid propagation by capillary forces and the detailed reconstruction of the fiber distribution allowed the interpretation of the flow progression in terms of the

capillary pressure and permeability factors.

The transport of small and large voids was also assessed by means of SXCT. Small voids were transported along the tow direction through the empty spaces between individual fibers. They were trapped when the distance between fibers was below a critical value because the pressure gradient required to overcome the capillary pressure was too high. As a result, a large volume fraction of very small voids was trapped in the microstructure. The propagation of a large void spanning dozens of fibers was also observed in the experiments. In this case, the void migrated easily along the fiber tow driven by the vacuum pressure gradient. Very interestingly, the internal pressure of the void was large enough to produce significant fiber and bag movements during the void transport, leaving a trail of smaller voids in the wake.

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Figure 1: a) Sketch of the rotating apparatus for tow infusion in the XCT synchrotron beamline. b) Detail of the infused tow and of the flow front position. c) XCT cross-section of tow and of the vacuum bag before infiltration.

Figure 2: a) Cross section of the fiber bundle within the vacuum bag. Fibers and voids are clearly visible while the differences between dry and wet regions are visible in the inlet *i1*. b) Detail of the fiber tow prior to the infusion. c) Detail of the partially impregnated fiber tow. d) Fully impregnated fiber tow. e) Sketch of the dual flow at the tow/fiber level observed during the impregnation experiments.

Figure 3: Longitudinal cross section of the impregnated tow showing trapped voids and the flow front meniscus. Local fiber misalignments with convergent/divergent trajectories are also visible.

Figure 4: Transverse cross-sections of the tow obtained from SXCT. a) Dry and wet regions, the latter shown in navy blue. b) Local fiber volume fraction, V_f . c) Longitudinal permeability factor, K_{\parallel}/D_f^2 , according to equation (4). d) Non-dimensional capillary pressure, \bar{p}_c , according to equation (3).

Figure 5: Constricted void transport through a capillary tube.

Figure 6: SXCT cross sections of the fiber tow showing the transportation during infiltration. a) Prior to infiltration. b) When the void is passing through the cross section. c) After impregnation. The fluid is shown in navy blue and the pore in red.